

Towards Lightweight Architectures for Embedded Machine Learning in Musical Instruments

Chris Kiefer

Experimental Music Technologies Lab, University of Sussex
c.kiefer@sussex.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

It can be challenging to engage with machine learning in restricted computing environments, such as the systems often in use in digital or hybrid musical instruments. We often use low power, low memory devices with limited computational power, and need high frequency models for sensor and sound processing. Conversely, contemporary machine learning and AI can be resource hungry, limiting its use in embedded systems. In previous research, the Stochastic Logic Optimisation algorithm offered a method of lightweight machine learning using two-state logic networks, intended for musical use in embedded systems. This experiment shows how this approach can be expanded on, using random boolean reservoirs, for signal generation. These initial results demonstrate the efficacy of a reservoir computing approach, built only from networks of lookup tables. They show that, for the task of training sine wave generators, reservoirs can be improved if built with hierarchical growth algorithms, and further improved by selecting inputs and outputs based on network centrality. The results also demonstrate successful use of Pulse Density Modulation for signal encoding.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many reasons for which we may want to embed machine learning (ML) processes within a physical musical instrument. Embedding, in this context, will refer to ML running on computing resources within a self-contained instrument, maybe connected to sensors, actuators, and/or input/output ports. Examples could be euro-rack modules, hybrid double basses or gestural controllers, among many other possibilities. These instruments may be defined as *smart* [1] or *intelligent* [2]. ML could be used for pattern recognition, sound generation, signal processing, again among many possibilities. We might embed ML for pragmatic reasons; it could be advantageous for an instrument to be portable, to take it to rehearsals and performances, expanding creative opportunity. It may be important to capture and process data quickly within an instrument, with minimum delay. For example, in a feedback instrument such as the halldorophone [3], delays in signal processing would affect the feedback loop and therefore

change the sound and behaviour of the instrument. Beyond pragmatic reasons, one can conceptualise machine learning in music and instrument design holistically; that is to consider all the typical processes in ML, data collection, training, inference, experimentation with architectures, as creative materials, as part of a broader musical engagement with ML. If this is the case, then surely our instruments are good interfaces for engaging with ML, beyond conventional interaction paradigms, and with embedded ML we might explore the value of seamless engagement with self-contained ML materials.

Our current batch of ML technologies are typically *heavyweight*; we have large models that can take hours, days or weeks to train, consuming large amounts of energy, memory and computing resources. The implications for musical instrument designer are that, to use these technologies, an instrument needs to be tethered to a powerful computer. This approach has several potential disadvantages; the interface to the instrument is spread across different interfaces and interaction styles, the instrument lacks portability, the connections can introduce latency, Some large models may not run in realtime, although projects such as RAVE [4] are focusing on this issue. To embed ML within an instrument, we need to use smaller computers or microcontrollers, that typically have restricted memory and processing resources. We may also want to run low-power devices, perhaps so we can use battery power for portability, or perhaps because it's challenging to try and quietly cool down powerful processing units that would dissipate a great deal of heat within a musical instrument.

Fortunately, low-powered machine learning (or TinyML) is a highly active research field. Outside of computer music applications, one can find successful models such as Bonsai [5], which run successfully in low memory environments without the need for hardware floating point processors. Models have also been configured to run on Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) (e.g LogicNets [6], LUTnets [7]), which offer further performance advantages.

Within the field of computer music, research into embedded ML within musical instruments is an emerging field. Possibly because of the challenging demands that musical instruments might place on ML models, embedding ML has been highly technically challenging. However, with increasingly powerful embedded computers (e.g. Teensy 4, EPSP32) and specialist embedded audio platforms (e.g. Bela, Daisy), and as FPGAs become more affordable with open source toolchains (e.g. Lattice ICE40), we have better hardware options to explore this field. As this hardware

collides with TinyML research, we are finding better technologies to experiment with in musical instrument design.

2. STOCHASTIC LOGIC OPTIMISATION

One response to the challenge of embedded musical ML is Stochastic Logic Optimisation (SLO). Where TinyML typically takes trained models and reduces and approximates them until they will run on a more restricted computer, SLO attempts to build fast models from the ground upwards, with basic computing resources. It's an algorithm for optimising feed-forward networks of lookup tables (LUTs), which are the raw material of typical FPGAs and easily translated to run on microcontrollers. A lookup table is a logic block, usually with 4 or 6 inputs, a single output, and a block of data containing an output value for each possible combination of inputs. For example, a 4-input LUT will have a memory containing 16 binary output values, indexed by the value of the input.

LUT networks have the advantage of needing little memory, and running without the need for potentially expensive numerical processing, such as floating point arithmetic. SLO is described in detail in [8]. In brief, the algorithm is a supervised learning method; it takes a randomly initialised network of LUTs and adjusts their truth tables such that the network models the relationship between inputs and outputs in the training data set. It does this by presenting the data in batches to the network, collecting potential truth table adjustments using the heuristic of finding the most minimal adjustment to correct each error, and then applying the most popular of these adjustments.

Initial experiments with SLO focused on a simple beat prediction task. Having established the basic efficacy of the algorithm with this model, the next stage in development towards meaningful use of embedded in musical instruments is to explore more complex signal processing. In the next section, new architectural options for supporting this task are explored, before an experiment to explore their value is reported on.

3. NEW MODEL ARCHITECTURE

3.1 Modelling Time

Representation of time is key to most machine learning models that will be used within musical instruments. Broadly speaking, time in typical machine learning architectures might be represented in one of three ways:

1. Stateless models, with time represented in the data. For example, a feed-forward network of LUTs, as mentioned above, has no memory, so time must be modelled in the training data. Each frame of data might contain a history of the most recent values in the input signal.
2. Stateless models, with feedback from output to input. With a feedback connection, the stateless model becomes a kernel in a dynamical system, giving the model a time-varying reaction to new input.

3. Stateful models, possibly also with output-input feedback connections. These models have internal recurrent connections, and therefore retain their own memory of previous input and internal states.

In the context of this project, stateful models seem most appealing for realtime signal processing. Time and function are united in the model, meaning that any adjustments to the model will be coherent across both domains. This could make training conceptually more simple. This coherence might improve the models potential for realtime manipulation (for example, manipulation of CCRNNs [9]) or network bending approaches [10].

3.1.1 Random Boolean Networks as Reservoirs

In the search for a realtime approach to recurrent machine learning models, reservoir computing [11] offers potentially valuable solutions. In the reservoir computing paradigm, a randomly constructed recurrent model (the reservoir) is paired with a stateless feed-forward model (the readout). In training, observations are collected of how the reservoir reacts to input over time, and the readout is optimised to make predictions based on these observations. The reservoir essentially provides time-varying state to a stateless model, and also functions to map signals into a higher dimensional space which can offer new perspectives on the input data.

Reservoirs can take many forms; a typical configuration is the one used in Echo State Networks [12], with continuously valued neurons updated in discrete time steps. Previous research has also explored boolean reservoirs, in the form of Random Boolean Networks (RBNs). RBNs were introduced by Kauffman [13] as a method for exploring complex dynamics between genes. More recent research has demonstrated the value of RBNs in reservoir computing [14], including successful implementation on FPGAs [15]. Constructed with simple LUTs, RBNs offer a straightforward and lightweight method for reservoir construction using basic computing resources. Previous research has combined RBNs with conventional readout layers, which might run too slowly on embedded systems due to the need for floating point processing. A model that combines an RBN with a trainable LUT network as a readout layer could offer a lightweight architecture for realtime signal processing. For simplicity, this combined model can be called a SLORBN. Figure 1 illustrates a small-scale example of this architecture.

3.1.2 Reservoir Design

An RBN is a network of LUTs. Typically, when used as reservoirs, RBNs are connected together with an architecture determined by linear probability; these *monolithic* reservoirs have no globally imposed structure. Xuan et al [16] propose an approach to structuring networks to resemble the structure of real-world networks. Their growth algorithm builds networks with hierarchically connected modules. This algorithm has been investigated in the design of RBN reservoirs [17], showing that *modular* reservoirs outperform monolithic reservoirs in temporal tasks: pattern detection, food foraging, and memory recall. These

Figure 1: An example of a SLORBN model. The entire model is constructed from LUTs. The input and readout layers are connected to subsets of RBN nodes.

results show promise for further exploration of signal processing tasks that might be useful in musical instrument design. The difference between modular and monolithic RBNs is illustrated in Figure 2. It shows two examples of connectivity in randomly generated 500 node RBNs, the modular RBN exhibiting visible structure across small communities of nodes.

An unexplored extension to reservoir architecture design is the selection of points of connection to inputs and to the readout layer. In examples in the research literature, these are typically chosen with linear probability. Perhaps modular reservoirs, through more structured design, offer optimal connection points compared to random selection?

3.2 Signal Encoding

If we are to use LUT networks as signal processors in musical instruments, RBNs offer a solution to embedded time into the models, but how do we represent continuous signals to processors that work only with binary logic? There are many ways in which numbers can be represented, with standard binary or binary encoded decimal encodings, or using sparse positional encodings such as one-hot encoding. These types of encodings might be challenging because of the demands put onto the model to engage with the encoding abstraction. If binary number encodings are used, the model will have the additional demands of learning to process binary abstractions. Positional encoding will force the models to use large architectures to cope with the scale of inputs and outputs, for example a one-hot encoded 8 bit number would need 256 inputs to connect it to the network.

A third option is the use of Pulse Density Modulation (PDM) [18]. With PDM, a continuous signal is encoded in binary as a series of high-frequency pulses. Figure 3 shows an example, where a sinewave has been encoded

using PDM, with 8x oversampling. A continuous signal can be recovered from the PDM signal using a low-pass filter. This system is very commonly used in sigma-delta conversion in DACs and ADCs. In relation to AI and ML, PDM sits within a broader class of *time-based* signal representations that have a neurobiological basis, and are being explored within neuromorphic computing [19] and with spiking neural networks (e.g. [20]). The applications of PDM in computer music and machine learning are under-explored research areas.

Within the SLORBN architecture, the PDM signal is fed into the RBN reservoir and a randomly predetermined subset of the reservoir states are collected. Figure 4 shows an example of these states. The model is then trained with SLO to map from these states to the PDM-encoded target output. During inference, the output of the model is low-pass filtered to recover a continuous signal.

The use of PDM encoding to represent signals in RBNs and LUT networks could be advantageous because it does not impose any extra abstractions on the model, the signal is already using the raw representations that the model is working with. The potential disadvantage is that PDM signals require a higher sample rate than the source signal being encoded, which may also have a follow-on effect of needing larger networks, both of which impose additional demands on computing resources.

4. EXPERIMENT: TRAINING SIGNAL GENERATORS

So far, some key issues have been explored in how trainable LUT networks can be expanded to work as signal processors. A potentially valuable architecture is the SLORBN: a combination of RBN reservoirs with LUT network readout layers, trained using SLO. The following questions could be considered:

Figure 2: Examples of connectivity in 500 node RBNs, with connections determined by (a) linear probability and (b) Xuan et al’s hierarchical growth algorithm

Figure 3: An example of Pulse Density Modulation encoding: a sine wave and the corresponding bit pattern, using 8x oversampling.

1. Does this architecture enable the training of signal processors?
2. How should reservoirs be designed optimally for signal processing? e.g. are monolithic or modular reservoirs better?
3. How should input and output nodes be selected in the reservoir?
4. Is PDM encoding effective for signal processing with these models?

4.1 Method

Inspired by early reservoir computing experiments in trainable sine wave generation [21], an experiment was designed to begin exploration these questions. The task in the experiment was to train a sine wave generator using SLORBN models. This task is a good test of time representations in the model; a sine wave moves in different directions from identical values in each half of the waveform. Without historical context, the model cannot determine which value to produce next.

Full sourcecode for the experiment can be found in the accompanying repository¹. The original signal was a sine wave, with a 16 sample wavelength. This signal was PDM encoded with 2x oversampling (a higher rate was not necessary because of the lack of high frequency content). To generate a dataset, the PDM signal was repeated 4 times, and then copied into input-output pairs such that the model would be trained to predict the next sample in the signal.

During the experiment, reservoirs were generated in a variety of configurations. They were either monolithic, or were generated using Xuan et. al’s hierarchical growth algorithm, with $M = 4$, $n = 4$ and $m_0 = 2$. Inputs and outputs to the reservoir were selected with one of four algorithms, as shown in table 1. The most basic scheme was to choose nodes with linear probability (**RAND**). It seemed interesting to explore the connectivity within the reservoir and select points based on this information. Reservoirs were analysed using betweenness centrality [22], which essentially measures the importance of each node in a network. Nodes were selected with higher probability for high (**BCH**) or low (**BCL**) betweenness centrality. The final selection technique (**MOD**) applies only to modular

¹ https://github.com/chriskiefer/SLO_RBN

Figure 4: An example of activity within a Random Boolean Network. A 500 node RBN was perturbed by two cycles of a PDM encoded sine wave; this figure shows how the outputs of a subset of these nodes varied over time.

networks; nodes were selected from a minimal set of low-level modules within the hierarchy.

The experiment consisted of multiple trials, where an attempt was made to train a model with this dataset, with randomly selected variations in parameters. Each trial ran as follows:

1. A 500 node reservoir was generated, with a randomly chosen configuration for (a) generation method, (b) input selection and (c) output selection. Table 1 shows these configurations. The numbers of input and output nodes were fixed at 30% for input and 15% for output (manual tuning showed these values to be capable of producing reasonable results). The reservoir generation algorithms were tuned so that the average connectivity in all reservoirs was likely to be close to 2 inputs per node. Reservoirs with this value, referred to as K in RBN literature, exhibit behaviour at the border between order and chaos [23], and are most suited for computation.
2. The input signal was fed into the reservoir, and the corresponding states were collected
3. These states, together with the target output signal, were combined into a dataset, and used to train a LUT network, using SLO. All LUT networks had the following number of nodes per layer: [4096, 1024, 256, 64, 16, 4, 1]. Training took place over 600 iterations, with a batch size of 32. Again, these values were selected using manual tuning, such that all configurations had the potential to produce reasonable results.
4. The trained LUT network was evaluated on the original set of reservoir states to obtain an accuracy score, measured as the percentage of correct predictions.

Once successfully trained, a model could be used as a sine wave generator by cueing the reservoir from its original state, and then feeding the output from the model back into the inputs.

4.2 Results

The experiment took place over a total of 25000 trials, split equally across the configurations. Results are shown in figure 5. The results show that the highest scoring networks

Config	Reservoir Type	Inputs	Outputs
0	Monolithic	RAND	RAND
1		BCH	BCH
2		BCL	
3		BCH	BCL
4		BCL	
5	Modular	RAND	RAND
6		BCH	BCH
7			BCL
8			MOD
9		BCL	BCH
10			BCL
11			MOD
12		MOD	BCH
13			BCL
14			MOD

Table 1: Configurations for generating reservoirs in the experiment

were modular, with both inputs and outputs selected based on high betweenness centrality. Monolithic networks with an identical selection method were the second highest scoring. In all comparable cases except BCH/BCL, modular networks had a higher average accuracy than monolithic networks.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This experiment has explored the value of potential expansions of LUT networks and the SLO algorithm, towards applications in embedded ML in musical instruments. It tested a new architecture, where time is represented within a Random Boolean Network reservoir, and the feed-forward readout layer of LUTs is trained with SLO, based on observations from the reservoir.

The experiment shows that this architecture is capable, with high accuracy, of training models as PDM-encoded sine wave generators at low resolution (16 samples, 2x oversampling). The model further explored reservoir generation, input and output connectivity and signal encoding schemes. The results showed that in the specific context of this task, hierarchical modular reservoirs had higher average accuracy than monolithic ones in all but one comparable configuration. This is consistent with results from other comparisons of these network structures. The results on input/output node selection showed that selecting both

Figure 5: A boxplot of results of the experiment, showing % accuracy for each configuration, as detailed in table 1. The white dots show the averages.

input and output nodes with probability proportional to betweenness centrality gave the best results with both monolithic and modular RBNs.

Pulse Density Modulation encoding has been shown to work well with this architecture, on the basis that high accuracy scores were obtained. This experiment did not compare PDM to other encoding schemes, but it does establish basic efficacy for its use with SLORBN models. The challenge with this encoding is that the model must be oversampled if it needs to respond to or generate higher frequencies. In implementation, this places a burden on microcontrollers because of their sequential processing architecture. FPGAs, in contrast, are ideal for this task, because of the way in which they can be configured with massively parallel LUT circuits. RBNs can be run in a single clock cycle (potentially taking low numbers of nanoseconds) or even unclocked [15] at the maximum speed of the circuitry. Speed in FPGA implementations is independent of scale because of parallelism. Similarly, the readout networks can run at one clock cycle per layer. On both FPGAs and microcontrollers, PDM signals can be output directly to a digital pin, and filtered with relatively simple analogue circuitry to recover the underlying signal. PDM processing certainly has interesting potential, and deserves further exploration.

While these results are promising, there is still some way to go towards creating models that work at a resolution high enough for full-frequency audio, while also balancing a minimal architecture for embedded systems. Further investigation showed that the most successful configuration (6) could produce 100% accurate models with a smaller architecture of a 200 node RBN and readout layer sizes of [256, 65, 16, 4, 1], utilising 9.1% of the resources of the models used in the original experiment. Further

work should explore the effects of raising resolution in this configuration, to achieve higher oversampling rates and to test higher bandwidth and lower frequency waveforms.

This experiment establishes foundations for an architecture for SLO training and LUT networks that can be used for signal generation. It also raises some interesting questions. While this experiment demonstrates the potential for signal generation, it does not explicitly explore signal processing. For example, how can these models be trained to modulate the signal they are generating? How can they be trained as filters? Another potentially valuable avenue is in network bending. With modular reservoirs, we have plenty of information about their structure, with the addition of information about nodes centrality from network analysis. Perhaps this information can inform network bending approaches, and offer points for manipulation of these models?

Future work will explore hierarchical architectures in trainable LUT networks and to develop further creative applications. It will also focus on finding meaningful benchmarks for these models on various low-power computing devices.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] L. Turchet, “Smart musical instruments: vision, design principles, and future directions,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 8944–8963, 2018.
- [2] T. Magnusson, “Of epistemic tools: Musical instruments as cognitive extensions,” *Organised Sound*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 168–176, 2009.
- [3] H. Úlfarsson, “Feedback mayhem. compositional affordances of the halldorophone discussed by its users,”

- in *Proceedings of the 2019 International Computer Music Conference*, 2019.
- [4] A. Caillon and P. Esling, “Rave: A variational autoencoder for fast and high-quality neural audio synthesis,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.05011*, 2021.
- [5] A. Kumar, S. Goyal, and M. Varma, “Resource-efficient machine learning in 2 kb ram for the internet of things,” in *International Conference on Machine Learning*. PMLR, 2017, pp. 1935–1944.
- [6] Y. Umuroglu, Y. Akhauri, N. J. Fraser, and M. Blott, “Logicnets: Co-designed neural networks and circuits for extreme-throughput applications,” in *2020 30th International Conference on Field-Programmable Logic and Applications (FPL)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 291–297.
- [7] E. Wang, J. J. Davis, P. Y. Cheung, and G. A. Constantinides, “LUTNet: Rethinking inference in FPGA soft logic,” in *2019 IEEE 27th Annual International Symposium on Field-Programmable Custom Computing Machines (FCCM)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 26–34.
- [8] C. Kiefer, “Stochastic optimisation of lookup table networks, for realtime inference on embedded systems,” in *2nd Conference on AI Music Creativity*, 2021.
- [9] —, “Sample-level sound synthesis with recurrent neural networks and conceptors,” *PeerJ Computer Science*, vol. 5, p. e205, 2019.
- [10] M. Yee-King and L. McCallum, “Studio report: sound synthesis with ddsp and network bending techniques,” in *2nd Conference on AI Music Creativity*, 2021.
- [11] M. Lukoševičius, H. Jaeger, and B. Schrauwen, “Reservoir computing trends,” *KI-Künstliche Intelligenz*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 365–371, 2012.
- [12] H. Jaeger, “The “echo state” approach to analysing and training recurrent neural networks—with an erratum note,” *Bonn, Germany: German National Research Center for Information Technology GMD Technical Report*, vol. 148, no. 34, p. 13, 2001.
- [13] S. Kauffman, S. A. Kauffman *et al.*, *At home in the universe: The search for laws of self-organization and complexity*. Oxford University Press, USA, 1995.
- [14] D. Snyder, A. Goudarzi, and C. Teuscher, “Finding optimal random boolean networks for reservoir computing,” in *ALIFE 2012: The Thirteenth International Conference on the Synthesis and Simulation of Living Systems*. MIT Press, 2012, pp. 259–266.
- [15] S. Apostel, N. D. Haynes, E. Schöll, O. D’Huys, and D. J. Gauthier, “Reservoir computing using autonomous boolean networks realized on field-programmable gate arrays,” in *Reservoir Computing*. Springer, 2021, pp. 239–271.
- [16] Q. Xuan, Y. Li, and T.-J. Wu, “Growth model for complex networks with hierarchical and modular structures,” *Physical Review E*, vol. 73, no. 3, p. 036105, 2006.
- [17] S. K. Cherupally, ““hierarchical random boolean network reservoirs,” Master’s thesis, 2018.
- [18] T. Kite, “Understanding PDM digital audio,” *Audio Precision*, 2012.
- [19] N. C. Sevuktekin, L. R. Varshney, P. K. Hanumolu, and A. C. Singer, “Signal processing foundations for time-based signal representations: Neurobiological parallels to engineered systems designed for energy efficiency or hardware simplicity,” *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 38–50, 2019.
- [20] M. Bensimon, S. Greenberg, and M. Haiut, “Using a low-power spiking continuous time neuron (sctn) for sound signal processing,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 4, p. 1065, 2021.
- [21] H. Jaeger, M. Lukoševičius, D. Popovici, and U. Siewert, “Optimization and applications of echo state networks with leaky-integrator neurons,” *Neural networks*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 335–352, 2007.
- [22] M. Barthelemy, “Betweenness centrality in large complex networks,” *The European physical journal B*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 163–168, 2004.
- [23] S. H. Strogatz, *Nonlinear dynamics and chaos: with applications to physics, biology, chemistry, and engineering*. CRC press, 2018.